

Need of Effective Communication Skills in Teaching Social Science in Classroom Situation

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Abstract

Educational technology believes that teachers are not only born but an ordinary person can be made a successful and effective teacher by training. Teaching affects learning directly and indirectly both. For making interaction more successful, the essential requirement is teacher effectiveness. He is the initiator, coordinator and director of the classroom interaction. Communication is a skill and it could be acquired through proper training. It takes presence of mind and courage to face people with the power to prove what they want to convey through communication. It is a basic social process required for the growth and development of individuals, groups, society and people. So to make classroom teaching effective, the teacher should acquire the different communication skill.

Keywords: Communication Skill, Teaching Methods, Social Science, Classroom Situation.

Introduction

What is 'communication'? According to the Concise Oxford Dictionary the word means 'the act of imparting, especially news', or 'the science and practice of transmitting information'. These definitions clearly show the link between 'teaching' and 'communication': teachers are constantly imparting new knowledge, or transmitting information. Communication skills are important for the presentation of a lesson or lecture in class. Communication skills for teachers are thus as important their in-depth knowledge of the particular subject which they teach. Teachers should be aware of the importance of communication skills in teaching. They must also realize that all students have different levels of strengths and weaknesses. It is only through communication skills that a teacher can introduce creative and effective solutions to the problems of the students. Thus, a teacher can enhance the learning process. A teacher, who is able to communicate well with students, can inspire them to learn and participate in class.

Educational technology believes that teachers are not only born but an ordinary person can be made a successful and effective teacher by training. That means the teaching of any teacher can be improved by drilling different strategies, techniques and skills of teaching. In this way, many teaching skills and techniques could be developed by the science of educational technology in order to transform teaching from art to science. Teaching affects learning directly and indirectly both.

Effective communication skills of a teacher in the classroom brings successful modification of behavior of students as desired by the process. Communication has special significance in teaching process and the form and nature of communication vary from person to person, culture to culture and society to society. There is great difference in the subject-matters of science, mathematics, literature etc. due to this reason different teaching skills are required for teaching different subjects.

Classroom teaching involves four elements i.e. the Teacher, message, medium and students. So, good teaching involves the effective use of all these components. For making interaction more successful, the essential requirement is teacher effectiveness. He is the initiator, coordinator and director of the

classroom interaction. There are some teachers who know more facts about their subject but they fail to communicate their thoughts, ideas and feeling to the students. On the contrary, there are also some teachers rated as average in terms of their educational or training background, but they acquired skills of communication effectively. They make their teaching more effective and clear by using various effective teaching strategies. Lecture-demonstration method is used by good Social Science teachers for imparting Social Science education in class room. By using this method it is possible to easily impart concrete experiences to students during the course of a lesson when the teacher wants to explain some abstract points. This method combines the instructional strategy of 'information imparting' and 'showing how'. This method combines advantages of both the lecture method and the demonstration method.

Social Science teachers should encourage more direct experimentation by children in order to help children broaden their range of fact finding skills beyond three T's - *Teacher, Textbooks, Television*. Classroom communication is not a mere one-sided presentation of facts; it requires inter communication between student and the teacher. Good teachers communicate ideas effectively, so that students also communicate their reactions by asking, participating, responding and behaving appropriately.

Different teachers have different styles of teaching. Some teachers like to talk, and expect the students to write down what they say and to learn it (this style encourages superficial learning - and rapid forgetting!). Other teachers see their role as one of helping the students to learn at a deeper level - to understand new ideas and concepts so well that they can apply them in a work situation. Either way, these teachers will do a better job if they communicate well with their students.

An important element of communication in teaching is the use of teaching aids. We have all heard the saying: 'What I hear, I forget; what I see, I remember; what I do, I know'. Pictures, written posters and practical demonstrations improve communication and we should use them as much as possible. Most of us have access to paper, posters, a chalkboard, or an overhead projector. We can use these to prepare aids for our lessons; summaries of important facts, or pictures and diagrams. The overhead projector is particularly useful, because it allows us to face our students while using it.

How could we know whether we are communicating well as a teacher? Communication is a skill - and we improve our skills by getting feedback on the way we perform them. We can get such feedback by asking an experienced colleague to sit in on our teaching, and to give us feedback. We can also ask someone to record us on a videotape as we teach which we then inspect critically afterwards. In either case the feedback will be better if we use a checklist to judge our performance. Teachers communicate by speaking, but also by writing.

Types of Communication

Based on the channels used for communicating, the process of communication can be broadly classified as verbal communication and non-verbal communication. Verbal communication includes written and oral communication whereas the non-verbal communication includes body language, facial expressions and visuals diagrams or pictures used for communication.

1. Verbal Communication -

Verbal communication is further divided into written and oral communication. The oral communication refers to the spoken words in the communication process. Oral communication can either be face-to-face communication or a conversation over the phone or on the voice chat over the Internet. Spoken conversations or dialogs are influenced by voice modulation, pitch, volume and even the speed and clarity of speaking. The other types of verbal communication are written communication. Written communication can be either via snail mail, or email. The effectiveness of written communication depends on the style of writing, vocabulary used, grammar, clarity and precision of language.

2. Non Verbal Communication

Non-verbal communication includes the overall body language of the person who is speaking, which will include the body posture, the hand gestures, and overall body movements. The facial expressions also play a major role while communication since the expressions on a person's face say a lot about his/her mood. On the other hand gestures like a handshake, a smile or a hug can independently convey emotions. Non verbal communication can also be in the form of pictorial representations, signboards, or even photographs, sketches and paintings.

Effective Communication Skills for Teachers-

Following are some of the communication skills that a teacher must possess so that they interact properly with the students -

1. Positive Motivation -

This is one of the important things that a teacher must possess. In a class, students always have different kinds of taste and preferences over subjects. So it is the job of the teacher to create enthusiasm and interest in the minds of the students towards a subject. It is also a teacher's role to remove any fear and inhibitions that a student may have towards a subject.

2. Effective Body Language -

This is the most powerful communication skill that a teacher must possess. Good presentation skills include a powerful body language supported by verbal skills. This can create a long lasting impression in the minds of the students. Thus, a teacher's lecture will inevitably become more interactive and interesting for the students. Besides, a teacher should maintain the volume, tone and rhythm of their voice during a lecture.

3. Sense of Humor -

The importance of this factor has been regularly underestimated. A good sense of humor keeps the students active and interested in the teacher's class. Teachers who are dour and lack humor do not contribute to the overall well being of the students.

4. Understanding the Students -

Teachers should encourage students to communicate openly. There should be emphasis on cultivating a dialogue rather than a monologue. So while solving any kind of problems in the classroom, it is always wise to hear the opinions of the students also.

5. Team Formation -

This is a good method where you can divide the classroom into small teams and ask them to solve different problems or complete assignments. This practice will increase not only the interaction among the students but also among the teachers and students.

6. Technical Skills -

It is also important that teachers should be up to date with all the latest teaching aids like computers, video conferencing and especially the use of internet. This will also help the students to keep up their interest in the learning process.

Lastly, we knew that Communication is a skill and it can be acquired through proper training. It also required conscious knowledge and strategic judgment. Every teacher should know different communication skills for classrooms viz,

- Using goal setting as a teaching tool
- Developing interest in the subject
- Developing problem solving skills
- Encouraging cooperative learning

- Encouraging creativity
- Encouraging students to experiment and explore
- Fostering independent thinking
- Overcoming the fear of making a mistake among students
- Practicing effective questioning
- Encouraging self-evaluation
- Employing team work in the classroom.

Using the above skills a teacher can make effective communication in a classroom.

Conclusion

The procedure of communication is a dynamic concept and not a stationary. Communication is a skill and it could be acquired through proper training. It takes presence of mind and courage to face people with the power to prove what they want to convey through communication. A communication can be said successful only if we are able to convince people for whatever we wanted to convey. Depending on the environment and circumstances the effectiveness of communication skills being affected by many variables. It is a basic social process required for the growth and development of individuals, groups, society and people. Knowing good communication skills are really important in every walk of life. So to make class room teaching effective, the teacher should acquire the different communication skill.

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